

BENDING RESPONSE OF SANDWICH PANELS WITH GRADED CORE: 3D ELASTICITY ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of an investigation into the behaviour of sandwich panels, with stiffness of the core graded in the thickness direction, on the basis of the recently developed 3D elasticity solution. The use of graded core to improve performance of sandwich structures, especially under localised loading, is examined and discussed.

Keywords: Sandwich structures; Functionally graded material; Bending; 3D elasticity

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels, considered to be a class of structural composites, are used in a wide variety of applications including aircraft, aerospace, naval/marine, construction and transportation industries where strong, stiff and light structures are required [1].

A sandwich panel consists of two thin, stiff and strong outer face sheets, separated by and bonded to a thick lightweight core with relatively low modulus of elasticity. Due to the mismatch of stiffness properties between the face sheets and the core, sandwich panels are susceptible to delamination, caused by high interfacial stresses, especially under localised or impact loading [2].

To increase the resistance of sandwich panels to failure of this type, which is currently a major problem in sandwich panel construction, the concept of functionally graded material (FGM) is actively explored in sandwich panel design. FGM refers to heterogeneous composite material with gradient compositional variation of the constituents from one surface of the material to the other, which results in continuously varying material properties [3–5]. Currently, a number of approaches to produce functionally graded core materials are being developed by materials scientists [6-8].

Various aspects of mechanical behaviour of sandwich panels with FGM core have been investigated. Anderson [9] developed a 3D elasticity solution for a sandwich panel with orthotropic face sheets and an isotropic functionally graded core subjected to transverse loading. Kashtalyan and Menshykova [10] recently developed a three dimensional elasticity analysis of sandwich panels with functionally graded core whose shear moduli vary exponentially through the thickness of the core. Apetre, Sankar and Ambur [11] investigated several available sandwich beam theories for their suitability of application to sandwich plates with functionally graded core.

The effect of localised loading on sandwich panels with homogenous core has been examined theoretically by a number of researchers. Polyakov [12] developed analytical expressions for local stresses and displacements under loading by point forces. Using an exact 3D solution for simply supported sandwich panels developed by Pagano [13] and Srinivas and Rao [14], Swanson [15] extended this solution to cover localised loading and compared it to results from higher order plate theory and classical theory. Whitney [16] developed a bending theory for a three-layer sandwich plate subjected to a distributed load and to an end-loaded cantilever plate under cylindrical concentrated bending.

Frostig and Thomsen [17] focused on the nonlinear response of sandwich panels in areas surrounding concentrated loads and stiffened core regions.

The effects of localised loading on sandwich panels have been also explored experimentally. Suvorov and Dvorak [18] evaluated the overall and local deflections of a sandwich plate under local contact from a rigid indenter and Koissin and Shipsha [19] and Lolive and Berthelot [20] analysed the effects of localised loading on the core material.

Etemadi, Khatibi and Takaffoli [21] presented a finite element analysis of low velocity impact behaviour of sandwich beams with a functionally graded core.

It is worth pointing out that all of the above studies into localised loading of sandwich panels [12-21] apart from Etemadi, Khatibi and Takaffoli [21] do not consider a functionally graded core.

This paper investigates the elastic deformation of sandwich panels with functionally graded core subjected to transverse loading in the framework of the three dimensional elasticity theory employing a recently developed solution [10]. This solution is extended to cover the effects of load localisation and a comparative study of two types of sandwich panels is carried out to examine the effect of load localisation and stiffness gradient in the core on the stress and displacement fields in the panels.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

A sandwich panel of length a , width b and total thickness $h_0 = 2h$ is referred to a Cartesian co-ordinate system xyz ($0 \leq x \leq a$, $0 \leq y \leq b$, $-h \leq z \leq h$) and assumed to be symmetric with respect to the mid-plane, with the core thickness $2h_c$ and the face sheet thickness h_f . Let us assume that the core, which is subdivided into two layers ($k = 2,3$) for the sake of convenience, and the face sheets ($k = 1,4$) are all FGMs, with constant Poisson's ratios $\nu^{(k)} = const$. The shear moduli of the core layers are assumed to vary exponentially through the thickness from the G_f value at the face sheet/core interface to the G_c value at the mid-plane according to

$$G^{(k)}(z) = G_c \exp\left(\gamma^{(k)} \frac{z}{h}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma^{(k)}$ are the inhomogeneity parameters

$$\gamma^{(k)} = (-1)^k \frac{h}{h_c} \ln \frac{G_c}{G_f} \quad (2)$$

The homogenous face sheets are treated as functionally graded materials with the inhomogeneity parameters, $\gamma^{(k)}$, sufficiently close to zero.

The face sheets are assumed to be perfectly bonded to the core, so that the continuity of stresses and displacements exists at the face sheet/core interfaces. The panel is subjected to transverse loading Q on the top surface,

$$Q(x, y) = - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_{mn} \sin \frac{\pi m x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi n y}{b} \quad (3)$$

where q_{mn} is the intensity of the loading at the centre of the panel and m and n are wave numbers. The bottom surface of the panel is assumed to be load-free.

The Navier-type boundary conditions are assumed at the edges which are representative of roller supports and analogous to simply supported edges in the plate theories. Details of the formulation and the representations of stress and displacement fields can be found elsewhere [10].

To investigate the bending response of sandwich panels with graded core under localised loading, $Q(x, y)$ was taken as

$$Q(x, y) = -q_{pr} \sin^{2p+1} \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin^{2r+1} \frac{\pi y}{b}, \quad (4)$$

where p and r are the load localisation degrees, q_{pr} is the intensity of the loading.

In order for a direct comparison, the intensity of the load for each degree of localised loading must be modified such that the overall load applied is the same in all cases. Using the identity,

$$\sin^{2n+1} x = \frac{(-1)^n}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{2n+1}{k} \sin[(2n+1-2k)x] \quad (5a)$$

where $\binom{2n+1}{k} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{k!(2n+1-k)!}$

localised loading can be represented as

$$Q(x, y) = -q_{pr} \frac{(-1)^p}{4^p} \sum_{k=0}^p (-1)^k \binom{2p+1}{k} \sin \left[(2p+1-2k) \left(\frac{\pi x}{a} \right) \right] \\ \times \frac{(-1)^r}{4^r} \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{2r+1}{k} \sin \left[(2r+1-2k) \left(\frac{\pi y}{b} \right) \right] \quad (5b)$$

Using double integrals, the factors by which the intensity of loading must be increased for different degrees of localisation can now be calculated. These are specified in table 1.

Table 1: Intensity of loading for varying degrees of localisation.

p, r	0 (standard load)	1	2	3
q_{pr}	1	2.25	3.5156	4.7852

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the stiffness gradient is taken as $G_c/G_f = 0.1$, the thickness of the face sheets is $h_f = 0.0125h_0$ and the Poisson's ratios for all layers are taken as $\nu^{(k)} = 0.3, k = 1, \dots, 4$.

The following figures (1-3) show through thickness variation of the normalised stresses $\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}/q_{pr}$ and normalised displacements $\bar{U}_i = \frac{G_f U_i}{q_{pr} h}$, for standard loading ($p = r = 0$) and increasing load localisation ($p = r = 1, 2, 3$). The effect of this variation in loading is compared for three square panels, the first two being thin ($a/h_0 = b/h_0 = 9$) and thick ($a/h_0 = b/h_0 = 3$) panels with functionally graded (FG) core (FGMC panels), and the third a thick ($a/h_0 = b/h_0 = 3$) panel with homogenous core (HC panel).

As the degree of load localisation is increased, the out-of-plane normal stress $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$ throughout the panel increases in a similar manner for thin and thick panels with functionally graded (FG) and homogenous core. This means the type of core has almost no effect on this stress component.

Through thickness variation of the transverse shear stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$ (Fig. 1A, B and C) shows an increase in the stress magnitude throughout the core as the localisation of load is increased. However in the thick panels (both FGMC and HC) this stress component rises to a peak in the upper section of the core, whilst staying almost symmetrical for the thin panel.

Plots of normalised in-plane normal stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$ (Fig. 2) show for both thin and thick panels with FG or homogeneous core that as the degree of load localisation is increased the stresses in the face sheets greatly increase, while the localisation has far less effect on the stresses in the core. We also see that the type of core has strong influence on these stress components. For the homogeneous core (Fig. 2B) there is a large discontinuity in both of these stresses at the face sheet / core interfaces. This

discontinuity, one of the inherent problems displayed by sandwich panels, is removed entirely through introduction of the graded core. The normalised in-plane shear stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ behaves in a similar manner.

As the load localisation is increased, displacements through the panel increase for both thick and thin panels regardless of core material. Through-thickness variation of the in-plane \bar{U}_x and out-of-plane \bar{U}_z displacements is shown in Fig. 3A, 3C and 3B, 3D respectively. The plot of normalised in-plane displacement for the thick FGMC panel (Fig. 3A) is highly non-linear, once again emphasizing the importance of three-dimensional stress analysis for sandwich panel applications.

Fig. 1. Through-thickness variation of the normalised transverse shear stress $\sigma_{xz}(0, 0.5b, z)$ under standard ($p = r = 0$) and localised loads ($p = r = 1; 2; 3$) for (A) thin FGMC panel; (B) thick FGMC panel; (C) thick HC panel

Fig. 2. Through-thickness variation of the normalised in-plane normal stress σ_{xx} (0.5a, 0.5b, z) under standard ($p = r = 0$) and localised loads ($p = r = 1;2;3$) for (A) thick FGMC panel; (B) thick HC panel

Fig. 3. Through-thickness variations of the normalised in-plane displacement U_x (0, 0.5b, z) under standard ($p = r = 0$) and localised loads ($p = r = 1;2;3$) for (A) thick FGMC panel; (C) thick HC panel; through-thickness variation of the normalised transverse displacement U_z (0.5a, 0.5b, z) under standard ($p = r = 0$) and localised loads ($p = r = 1;2;3$) for (B) thick FGMC panel; (D) thick HC panel

The effect of varying the stiffness gradient was also explored in this study. Four different stiffness gradients ($G_c/G_f = 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.05$), were compared for the three panels used previously: a thin square panel ($a/h_0 = b/h_0 = 9$) with FG core, a thick square panel ($a/h_0 = b/h_0 = 3$) with FG core and a thick square panel ($a/h_0 = b/h_0 = 3$) with homogenous core. The loading in all cases was standard loading as described by equation (4).

As the stiffness gradient is increased, there is little effect on the out-of-plane normal stress $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$ for thin and thick panels with both FG and homogenous core, confirming that this stress is largely unrelated to the core material.

Through thickness variation of transverse shear stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$ (Fig 4A and 4B) shows that as the stiffness gradient is increased, there is a decrease in the stress magnitude at the centre of the core, and an increase in this stress at the outer section of the core. When comparing the thick FGMC and thick HC panels, it can be seen that for the panel with homogeneous core, the stress at the interface between the face sheet and core increases as the stiffness gradient is increased. This effect is far less pronounced in the panel with FG core.

Fig. 4. Through-thickness variation of the normalised transverse shear stress σ_{xz} ($0, 0.5b, z$) under varying stiffness gradient ($G_c / G_f = 0.5; 0.2; 0.1; 0.05$) for (A) thick FGMC panel; (B) thick HC panel

The plots of normalised in-plane normal stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$ (Fig. 5) show that for the homogeneous core, increasing the difference in stiffness gradient between the face sheets and core increases the discontinuity at the interfaces and increases the stresses in the face sheets. These stresses remain almost unchanged for the functionally graded core. The normalised in-plane shear stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ behaves in a similar manner.

Study of through thickness in-plane displacement \bar{U}_x (Fig. 6A and 6B) shows that increasing stiffness gradient increases the magnitude of this displacement for both the homogenous and graded core, the increase being larger for the homogenous core. This plot is again highly non-linear, emphasizing the need for 3D stress analysis.

A similar result is seen for the transverse displacement \bar{U}_z (Fig. 7A and 7B) with an increase in this component for both core types. However the increased stiffness of the graded core provides a much smaller increase in displacement.

Fig. 5. Through-thickness variation of the normalised in-plane normal stress σ_{xx} (0.5a, 0.5b, z) under varying stiffness gradient ($G_c / G_f = 0.5; 0.2; 0.1; 0.05$) for (A) thick FGMC panel; (B) thick HC panel

Fig. 6. Through-thickness variation of the normalised in-plane displacement U_x (0, 0.5b, z) under varying stiffness gradient ($G_c / G_f = 0.5; 0.2; 0.1; 0.05$) for (A) thick FGMC panel; (B) thick HC panel

Fig. 7. Through-thickness variation of the normalised transverse displacement U_z (0.5a, 0.5b, z) under varying stiffness gradient ($G_c / G_f = 0.5; 0.2; 0.1; 0.05$) for (A) thick FGMC panel; (B) thick HC panel

CONCLUSIONS

Comparative study of two sandwich panels, one with graded and the other with homogenous core has shown that introduction of the functionally graded core removes the discontinuity in stresses at the interfaces and decreases both in-plane and out-of-plane displacements. However under localised loading it has been found that transverse shear stress concentrations can occur.

A study into the effects of stiffness gradient variation has shown that introduction of a functionally graded core increased the performance of thicker panels and removed problems due to high stiffness gradient present in homogenous panels.

Many of the plots produced were highly non-linear through the thickness, showing the importance of 3D stress analysis.

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